

Non-Fluctuating Target Detection in Fluctuating K-Distributed Interference and Noise

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Abstract—This paper deals with the problem of non-fluctuating target detection in the presence of a mixture of heavy tailed K-distributed clutter and independent noise. Prior papers have derived generalized likelihood ratio tests (GLRT) for this problem as well as approximations of the GLRT. These results show the required optimum processing and its vastly different efficiency as compared to similar results derived under standard Gaussian assumptions. In this study we examine the detection performance of several proposed detectors using numerical simulation techniques. We demonstrate their performance under different clutter and noise conditions. We also propose a two-stage detection scheme for a multi-observation multi-channel detection problem.

Index Terms—K distributed noise, generalized likelihood ratio test, extreme statistics

I. INTRODUCTION

Nearly all radar systems perform target detection in the presence of both noise and clutter. Noise naturally occurs in every radar receiver system as well as the external environment. Clutter is an entirely different phenomena. It is caused by re-scattering of transmitted radar energy and usually must be modeled with very different statistical models than typical noise processes. One application where radar clutter disagrees with the Gaussian model is high resolution low-grazing angle scenarios. It has been shown experimentally that sea clutter, observed under these conditions, exhibits large spikes. The associated amplitude probability distribution thus exhibits heavy-tails [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. In the past decade or more researchers have developed data models and detectors trying to capture these effects and the associated performance capability. The most widely known non-Gaussian sea clutter model is the compound-Gaussian distribution [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. This consists of modeling the clutter return signal as $c_t = \sqrt{\tau_t}g_t$, where $g_t \sim CN(0, \sigma_e^2)$ follows a complex Gaussian distribution with mean zero and variance σ_e^2 , and the texture component τ_t which is a positive random variable.

In some applications the texture component τ_t is considered unknown but deterministic. More often the texture component is considered random. Moreover if τ_t follows a Gamma distribution, then c_t is said to follow a K-distribution. In this paper we will consider two detection problems, the second being a variant of the first. We will now introduce the first problem. Consider the detection on a non-fluctuating target in the presence of additive K-distributed clutter and

white Gaussian noise. More specifically consider the following binary hypothesis test,

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : x_t &= \sqrt{\tau_t}g_t + n_t \\ H_1 : x_t &= a + \sqrt{\tau_t}g_t + n_t \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where x_t , $t = 1, \dots, M$, are a set of M independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) radar returns and where a is the target return. The target return is non-fluctuating from return to return, but is considered to have random phase, $a = b * e^{j2\pi\phi}$ where $\phi \sim U(0, 1)$ and b is constant. In fact, the model in (1) with scalar-valued observables may be treated as the description of scalar signals at the output of coherent processing over a coherent processing interval (CPI) of some duration. Here we will model the texture parameter as a Gamma distributed random variable $\tau_t \sim \gamma(\nu, \beta)$. In most scenarios we will consider detection performance with variation in ν but then set $\beta = 1/\nu$ so that the power in the texture component remains constant. The probability density function (PDF) of a gamma random variable is

$$f(x; \nu, \beta) = \frac{\beta^{-\nu}}{\Gamma(\nu)} x^{\nu-1} e^{-x/\beta}. \quad (2)$$

The clutter speckle component $g_t \sim CN(0, \sigma_e^2)$ and the independent noise component n_t is distributed $CN(0, \sigma_n^2)$.

Several key points have been identified about the above stated detection problem in prior work [15], [16], [17]. First, the presence of the white Gaussian noise component cannot be ignored. In cases where the clutter distribution is heavy tailed (low ν values), detection performance will be dominated by the texture value with the minimal value, thus driving the detection performance into the regime of the lower power white Gaussian noise component. Second, an analytic form of the PDF under neither hypothesis is available. This drives the performance analysis either to utilize approximations or fully numeric simulations. Third, prior research has identified detectors that are optimal under only Gaussian noise or K-distributed noise.

In this sections that follow we will evaluate the performance of two detectors either derived as optimal detectors under certain restrictive conditions or proposed as approximately optimal. A third detectors performance will also be analyzed to show its poor performance. In section II we will introduce the considered detectors and show their performance through numerical simulation. In Section III we will introduce a variant

of the primary detection problem and consider the performance of modified versions of the detectors proposed in Section II. Finally we will present our conclusions in Section IV.

II. DETECTION PERFORMANCE

In this section we will show the performance of three different detectors against the binary hypothesis test given above in (1). The first detector to be considered is the standard non-coherent detector, which would be optimal in this problem were there no clutter. The test statistic is given as:

$$y_{nc,M} = \sum_{t=1}^M |x_t|^2. \quad (3)$$

The second detector is a variant of an optimal detector for the case when only K-distributed noise is present. In this scenario in [15] an optimal detector is derived from an approximate log-likelihood function for a sequence of several i.i.d. pulse repetition intervals (PRI's). It was noted in [15], that the minimum over M sample most influences the test statistic and therefore the following approximate test statistic will be considered in this study,

$$y_{min,M} = \min_{t=1,\dots,M} |x_t|^2. \quad (4)$$

This test statistic will be referred to as the “minimum” detector as it selects the data sample with the minimum modulus squared as the final test statistic.

Alternatively, we will present the results of a third detector, which although not optimal in any sense for this problem, helps to illustrate the power of the “minimum” detector. This third detector will be called the “maximum” detector as it is based on the selection of the sample with the maximum modulus as the final test statistic. Note, while not optimal in this setting, it has been used in other settings to achieve near optimum detection performance with regards to data-combining on high resolution data sets [18].

$$y_{max,T} = \max_{t=1,\dots,T} |x_t|^2. \quad (5)$$

We will first show the detection performance of the three detectors (non-coherent integration, minimum, maximum) for the case when no clutter is present. This is common practice [19], [20] In this scenario and all that follow, the detection threshold has been chosen to achieve a constant false-alarm rate of $PFA=10^{-3}$. A separate threshold has been set for each detector. In figure 1 we see that the non-coherent detector outperforms the other two as expected. Results are shown for different values of M as a function of signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). SNR is defined as $SNR \equiv |a|^2/\sigma_n^2$. In figure 2 we consider the scenario with only clutter and no noise. We show the case for heavy-tailed clutter ($\nu = 0.2$). Here we define signal-to-clutter ratio (SCR) as $SCR \equiv |a|^2/\sigma_e^2$. In this scenario we can easily see that the “minimum” detector vastly outperforms the other detectors. In addition, its performance only improves as the number of samples M is increased. Now we will consider the scenario with clutter and noise. In figures 3 and 4 we consider two cases, $SNR=10dB$ and $SNR=3dB$,

Fig. 1. Detector Performance for the case with no clutter.

Fig. 2. Detector Performance for the case with only clutter.

respectively. Now it becomes apparent that the overall detector performance is influenced by both the clutter and the noise components. Even in the case of 10dB SNR, the minimum detector outperforms almost always. Only at rather high SCR where clutter is deeply immersed in Gaussian noise does the non-coherent detector slightly outperform. When the noise level becomes higher, in the case of $SNR=3dB$, then the non-coherent detector does outperform the “minimum” detector at higher SCR's. Here the detection problem is dominated by noise. Before proceeding to the second detection problem, we show one more example of how the three detectors behave in the presence of clutter and noise. In figure 5 the SCR has been fixed and the variation in performance is shown as a function of SNR. Here we see that the “minimum” detector outperforms the non-coherent detector so long as the SNR stays above 5dB. Also notice that once the SNR reaches about 15dB, no gain in detector performance is achieved, unless the interval M is increased. This suggests that excess SNR is not beneficial when the detection performance is limited by clutter not noise.

Fig. 3. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, fixed SNR = 10dB.

Fig. 5. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, fixed SCR = 10dB.

Fig. 4. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, fixed SNR = 3dB.

III. MULTI-CHANNEL DETECTION PROBLEM

In this section we consider an extension to the detection problem considered in (1). Motivated by the final result of the last section and by practical radar functionality, we consider the scenario where multiple channels are used for detection in addition to multiple samples M . Consider the use of Q channels where in the same noise, clutter, and signal model as in (1) holds, but the total radar transmit energy is spread over W channels, decreasing the per-channel SNR by a factor of $1/Q$.

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 : x_{t,q} &= \sqrt{\tau_{t,q}}g_t + n_{t,q} \\ H_1 : x_{t,q} &= a + \sqrt{\tau_{t,q}}g_t + n_{t,q} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where x_t , $t = 1, \dots, M$, $q = 1, \dots, Q$, are a set of MQ independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) radar returns from Q channels and M samples. The white Gaussian noise

component now as noise power σ_n^2/Q . The other model components stay the same as per (1). In practice, these Q channels might correspond to different non-overlapped radar frequencies.

We consider three variations of the original detectors examined above. In all case, we will a second stage detection step involving non-coherent integration over the additional Q channels. Formally, the three modified detectors will be defined as,

$$y_{nc-nc,Q,M} = \sum_{t=1}^M \sum_{q=1}^Q |x_{t,q}|^2, \quad (7)$$

$$y_{min-nc,Q,M} = \sum_{t=1}^M \min_{q=1, \dots, Q} |x_{t,q}|^2, \quad (8)$$

$$y_{max-nc,Q,M} = \sum_{t=1}^M \max_{q=1, \dots, Q} |x_{t,q}|^2. \quad (9)$$

Two scenarios have been simulated, one with an SCR of 0dB and the other with an SCR of -3dB. In both of these cases, the number of samples M has been fixed, but the number or channels W and SNR is varied. The results corroborate the findings of the single channels case in that as high enough SNR (SNR here is the single channel SNR before multiple channels are added) it is beneficial to add more sub channels and spread the radar energy out. We have assumed that the SCR will not change as more channels are added, because this ratio should be fixed based on the clutter scattering conditions. Once the SNR drops too low, it is no longer beneficial to add too many or more than 1 channel. In figures 6 and 7 these results are presented. At low SCR levels (high clutter) the advantage of more channels is more important. It has been assumed the that the clutter texture component remains independent not only from sample-to-sample, but from channel-to-channel. This is better for detection because

Fig. 6. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, multi-channel, fixed SCR = 0dB.

Fig. 8. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, multi-channel, fully correlated clutter texture, fixed SCR = -7dB.

Fig. 7. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, multi-channel, fixed SCR = -7dB.

Fig. 9. Detector Performance for the case with clutter and noise, multi-channel, fixed SCR = 0dB, SNR = 12dB

more independent clutter observations are made. However, it is reasonable to consider that scenario when the clutter texture component is fully correlated between the pulses/time samples. The authors of [21] also consider a similar scenario with possibly correlated clutter texture, but do so with only non-coherent integration. We have simulated this case and show the results in figure 8. Detection performance has decreased relative to the uncorrelated case. The final figure demonstrates that there is an optimum number of channels Q for a given number of sample values M . This assumes that the SNR and SCR are fixed.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have demonstrated through numerical simulations the performance of three simple detectors. This worked considered a mixture of K-distributed clutter and white Gaussian noise. This analysis furthers prior results by considering non-fluctuating targets. We have also proposed an

alternative detection problem wherein multiple independent channels are used to perform target detection. We should that utility of this scheme using altered versions of the initial three detectors. The analysis showed that there is benefit to using multiple channels in the presence of strong clutter as a means to gain additional independent clutter realizations. Performance decreases once the problem reverts to a noise limited case.

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